

Information Technology Students' Satisfaction of the Educational Tour 2015

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Abstract

Learning of students is both within and outside the classrooms. Believing on the opportunities provided by educational tour on students' learning, the Bachelor of Science in Information Technology of John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. includes educational tour as learning activity. This study aimed to determine the Information Technology students' satisfaction of their educational tour last October 6 to 9, 2015. The respondents of this study were the nineteen (19) students who joined the tour. Data used in this study were obtained from the furnished evaluation instrument attached to the learning journal of the students. Statistical tools used were mean and standard deviation. Results of this study revealed that students were "very satisfied" to "extremely satisfied" in various aspects of the educational tour in terms of the six components, namely: itinerary, program, transport service, hotel accommodation, food, and tour coordinators. As to overall, students were "extremely satisfied".

Introduction

Learning may also be acquired from experiences outside school campuses. Same or even better learning opportunities await students even in trips. It is not only limited to classrooms experiences.

A study (Shakil, Faizi, & Hafee, 2011) revealed the importance of fieldtrips at higher education. It was found out that fieldtrips are not only helpful in effective learning but also promote the qualities of leadership, discipline, and self-confidence among students. Furthermore, it was cleared that fieldtrips are beneficial for society and individuals and also promote the importance of culture and historical places. In another study, Greene, Kisida, & Bowen (2014) found out that enriching field trips contribute to the development of students into civilized young men and women who possess more knowledge about art, have stronger critical-thinking skills, exhibit increased historical empathy, display higher levels of tolerance, and have a greater taste for consuming art and culture.

Believing in the benefits of fieldtrips, John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. (JBLFMU-Molo) includes educational tour as one of the learning activities in all degree programs. JBLFMU-Molo's Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) degree program includes educational tour as a part of the requirements in Systems Analysis and Design with Educational Tour (SADET) course.

SADET is offered during the first semester of third year. This course covers the learning of the different tools and techniques to system development. It includes educational tour not only for exposure to various IT industries and business processes, but also for understanding of the roles of IT in the different systems ("SADET", n.d.). It is one of courses in the revised curriculum of BSIT effective academic year 2012-2013.

The first batch of students in the revised curriculum who took the SADET course was enrolled during the first semester, academic year 2014-2015. However, because of certain incident in relation to educational tour of certain school in the Philippines, the plan for the education tour of this batch was not pursued. With confirmation from the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), the second batch who took the said course during the first semester, academic year 2015-2016 participated in the educational tour last October 6 to 9, 2015.

Statement of the Problems

This study determined the satisfaction of the IT students in their educational tour last 2015. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions.

- 1) What is the satisfaction of the students in their educational tour as to various aspects?
- 2) What is the satisfaction of the students in their educational tour in terms of itinerary, program, transport service, hotel accommodation, food, and tour coordinators component, and overall satisfaction?

Significance of the Study

This study may be beneficial to teachers, students, tour coordinators, travel agency, and researchers.

Teachers who will handle the same course may take into consideration the results in preparing activities for the upcoming educational tours.

Students who will take the course and participate in the upcoming education tour may anticipate the possible satisfaction of the tour based on the experience of the participants in this study reflected through their evaluations.

Tour coordinators who handled the said tour may be informed of the participants' satisfaction on the service they rendered during the educational tour. Moreover, the results may suggest them should improvement must be done.

Travel agency may be informed of the quality service they provide and may consider the results in future business endeavors.

Other researchers in the field of academics and tourism may utilize the results of this study in their future research endeavors.

Delimitation of the Study

The respondents of this study were the BSIT students who joined the educational tour last October 6 to 9, 2015. They were officially enrolled in the SADET course last first semester, academic year, 2015-2016.

The data used in this study were taken from the evaluation instrument included in the learning journal for the said course. Data from all those who joined in the tour were utilized in the data processing. Statistical tools used were mean and standard deviation.

Methodology

This study made use of the descriptive research design.

Respondents of the Study

Out of the 20 students who were officially enrolled in SADET last first semester, academic year 2015-2016, 19 (95%) joined the educational tour. These 19 BSIT students of JBLFMU-Molo were considered as respondents of this study.

Instrumentation

This study utilized the evaluation tool included attached in the learning journal of the students for the SADET course.

The instrument contains 22 aspects of the educational tour, divided into six components. The first component is on itinerary consisting of three (3) aspects, namely: observance of schedule, pacing, and relevance of the companies visited. The second component is on program broken down into three (3) aspects: significance of the topics presented, adequacy on familiarization of the company, and expertise of the lecturer. The third component covers transport service with four (4) aspects: carefulness of the personnel, friendliness of the personnel, cleanliness of the transport, and comfort on the use of the transport. The fourth component measures hotel accommodation covering four (4) aspects, namely: cleanliness, friendliness of staff, location, and service. Fifth component on food covers two (2) aspects: choice of food served and sanitation. Finally, the sixth component is about tour coordinators with six (6) aspects: friendliness, knowledge of area, concern for safety, attitude, dependability, and promptness.

Each aspect is rated as excellent, very good, good, satisfactory, or poor with the weight of 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively.

To describe the students' satisfaction, an arbitrary scale below was used.

Scale		Satisfaction	
4.21	-	5.00	Extremely satisfied
3.41	-	4.20	Very satisfied
2.61	-	3.40	Moderately satisfied
1.81	-	2.60	Slightly satisfied
1.00	-	1.80	Not satisfied

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were utilized in analyzing the data.

Mean was used to describe the students' satisfaction of the educational tour in various aspects and their satisfaction in terms of itinerary, program, transport service, hotel accommodation, food, and tour coordinators component, and overall satisfaction.

Standard deviation was used to describe the dispersion in the satisfaction among students.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the various aspects and the corresponding students' satisfactions.

Table 1

Students' Satisfaction on Various Aspects of the Educational Tour

Components	Mean	Description	SD
<i>Itinerary</i>			
• Observance of schedule	4.11	Very satisfied	.809
• Pacing	4.26	Extremely satisfied	.653
• Relevance of the companies visited	4.26	Extremely satisfied	.872
<i>Program</i>			
• Significance of the topics presented	4.21	Extremely satisfied	.918
• Adequacy on familiarization of the company	4.05	Very satisfied	.911
• Expertise of the lecturer	4.32	Extremely satisfied	.671
<i>Transport Service</i>			
• Carefulness of the personnel	4.68	Extremely satisfied	.478
• Friendliness of the personnel	4.74	Extremely satisfied	.562
• Cleanliness of the transport	4.63	Extremely satisfied	.496
• Comfort on the use of the transport	4.63	Extremely satisfied	.597
<i>Hotel Accommodation</i>			
• Cleanliness	4.74	Extremely satisfied	.452
• Friendliness of Staff	4.58	Extremely satisfied	.692
• Location	4.58	Extremely satisfied	.507
• Service	4.79	Extremely satisfied	.419
<i>Food</i>			
• Choice of food served	4.47	Extremely satisfied	.697
• Sanitation	4.68	Extremely satisfied	.478
<i>Tour Coordinators</i>			
• Friendliness	4.84	Extremely satisfied	.375
• Knowledge of Area	4.74	Extremely satisfied	.452
• Concern for Safety	4.84	Extremely satisfied	.375
• Attitude	4.84	Extremely satisfied	.375
• Dependability	4.58	Extremely satisfied	.507
• Promptness	4.68	Extremely satisfied	.478

Students were “extremely satisfied” in the 20 aspects of the educational tour: pacing (M=4.26, SD=0.653) and relevance of the companies visited (M=4.26, SD=0.872) in terms of itinerary component; significance of the topics presented (M=4.21, SD=0.918) and expertise of

the lecturer (M=4.32, SD=0.671) in terms of program component; carefulness of the personnel (M=4.68, SD=0.478), friendliness of the personnel (M=4.74, SD=0.562), cleanliness of the transport (M=4.63, SD=0.496), and comfort on the use of the transport (M=4.63, SD=0.597) in terms of transport service component; cleanliness (M=4.74, SD=0.452), friendliness of staff (M=4.58, SD=0.692), location (M=4.58, SD=0.507), and service (M=4.79, SD=0.419) in terms of hotel accommodation component; choice of food served (M=4.47, SD=0.697) and sanitation (M=4.68, SD=0.478) in terms of food component; and friendliness (M=4.84, SD=0.375), knowledge of area (M=4.74, SD=0.452), concern for safety (M=4.84, SD=0.375), attitude (M=4.84, SD=0.375), dependability (M=4.58, SD=0.507), and promptness (M=4.68, SD=0.478) in terms of tour coordinators component. While, they were “very satisfied” only in the two aspects of the educational tour namely observance of schedule (M=4.11, SD=0.809) as to itinerary component and adequacy on familiarization of the company (M=4.05, SD=0.911) as to program component.

In terms of the dispersion on students’ satisfaction on various aspects of the educational tour, it was found to be less varied based on the obtained values of standard deviation. From among the various aspects, students’ satisfactions on the different aspects of tour coordinators component were the closest, while various aspects of program component were the widest.

Table 2 shows the students’ satisfaction on the six components and overall satisfaction.

Table 2
Students’ Satisfaction on the Six Components of the Educational Tour

Components	Mean	Description	SD
Itinerary	4.21	Extremely satisfied	.686
Program	4.19	Very satisfied	.714
Transport Service	4.67	Extremely satisfied	.391
Hotel Accommodation	4.67	Extremely satisfied	.433
Food	4.58	Extremely satisfied	.534
Tour Coordinators	4.75	Extremely satisfied	.311
Overall	4.51	Extremely satisfied	.390

Students were “extremely satisfied” on the following components of the educational tour: itinerary (M=4.21, SD=0.686), transport service (M=4.67, SD=0.391), hotel accommodation (M=4.67, SD=0.433), food (M=4.58, SD=0.534), and tour coordinators (M=4.75, SD=0.311). Moreover, they were also “extremely satisfied” as to overall satisfaction. However, they were “very satisfied” only as to program component (M=4.19, SD=0.714).

The dispersions in students’ evaluation as to the six components and overall satisfaction were less.

Conclusions

IT students who joined the educational tour had a high level of satisfaction. Their expectations on the various aspects of the tour were provided accordingly.

Although high levels of satisfaction were observed on the results, there are still some room for improvements especially on observance of schedule as to itinerary and adequacy on familiarization of the company.

The observed less dispersion on students' satisfaction showed that they had somehow similar level of expectations and perceptions of satisfaction on various aspects of the educational tour.

Recommendations

Teachers should look into the improvement specifically in terms of itinerary and program to ensure higher students' satisfaction on the succeeding educational tours.

Students are encouraged to give suggestions as regard to itinerary and program to ensure better observance of schedule and adequacy on familiarization of the company for the improvement of the succeeding educational tours.

Tour coordinators are encouraged to keep on providing quality service to consistently obtain high students' satisfaction.

Travel agency may take into consideration the improvement of the itinerary and program of the succeeding educational tours for IT students.

Researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies. Moreover, they are may take into consideration conducting a correlational study on students' satisfaction and their academic performance.

References

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